

Organic Pesticides. Part IX. Synthesis of some 2-Arylamino-4-substituted Phenylthiazoles and their Acetoxymercuri Derivatives

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Several 2-arylamino-4-substituted phenylthiazoles, derived from different arylthioureas and 4-fluoro-, 4-fluoro-2-methyl-, and 2-fluoro-5-methyl-acetophenones, have been prepared and their acetoxymercuri derivatives obtained in order to study their pesticidal properties.

Encouraged by considerable fungitoxicity exhibited by many fluoro-substituted thiazoles¹, we have now synthesised thiazoles having various modified fluorophenyl substitutions at 4-position of thiazole nucleus. With a view to enhancing the fungitoxicity, we have also prepared their corresponding acetoxymercuri derivatives, as similar acetoxymercurials of 2-substituted amino-4,5-dimethylthiazoles have already been shown to be powerful fungicides². Data on analogous fluoro-substitutions in thiazolyl nucleus, however, seem lacking in the literature.

The 2-arylamino-4-substituted phenylthiazoles have been prepared by condensing arylthioureas with different fluoro-acetophenones in presence of iodine, following the method of King and Hlavacek³. The arylthioureas have been prepared by the method of Douglass and Dains⁴.

The required fluoro-acetophenones have been prepared by the Friedel-Crafts acylation of fluorobenzene, *m*-fluorotoluene, and *p*-fluorotoluene respectively, following the method of Buu Hoi and Xuong⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL

m-Fluorotoluene was prepared by a modification of the Balz-Schieman reaction⁶ from *m*-toluidine (27g.) using sodium fluoborate in place of hydrofluoric acid; yield 15 g. (53.9%), b.p. 116-16.5°. Adams⁶ reports b.p. 114-15°.

p-Fluorotoluene was prepared by the above method from *p*-toluidine (36 g.); yield 23 g. (62.2%), b.p. 118-20°. Heilbron and Bunbury⁷ report b.p. 115.5°/756 mm.

Fluorobenzene was obtained by the method described earlier⁸.

1. Unpublished.
2. Das, Mohapatra, and Rout, *this Journal*, 1955, **32**, 55.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 3722.
4. *Ibid.*, 1934, **56**, 1408.
5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 386.
6. Adams, "Organic Reactions", Vol. V, pp. 203, 211.
7. "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", p. 558.
8. Joshi and Giri, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 117.

4-Fluoro,2-methylacetophenone was prepared after the method of Buu Hoi and Xuong⁵ by treating a mixture of *m*-fluorotoluene (15 g.) with acetyl chloride (12 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (24 g.) in dry CS₂ (50 ml); yield 11 g. (53%), b.p. 205-206° which corresponds to that previously recorded.

2-Fluoro-5-methylacetophenone was prepared by the above method from *p*-fluorotoluene (23 g.); yield 18 g. (56.6%), b.p. 206-207.5°. Buu Hoi and Xuong⁵ report b.p. 208-209°.

4-Fluoroacetophenone was prepared in above way from fluorobenzene (15 g.); yield 12 g. (55.8%) b.p. 80-81°/10-12 mm. Buu Hoi *et al*⁹. report b.p. 196°.

2-Arylamino-4-substituted Phenylthiazoles.—The experimental details have already been described in a communication to be published later¹ (Joshi and Giri). Only the thiazoles thus obtained are listed in Table I. The only exceptions in the usual isolation are compounds No. 3 and 7, where the thiazoles are soluble in NH₄OH, and therefore these have been isolated by precipitation with acetic acid. All the thiazoles were recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

Mercuriation of Thiazoles.—To a solution of the thiazole compound (1*M*) in ethanol-acetic acid were added the solution of mercuric acetate (1.3*M*) in water and acetic acid. In some cases the precipitate was obtained immediately, but in several cases precipitation occurred after several hours. In the latter case, the reaction mixture was kept overnight, filtered, and the mercurial obtained was purified by repeated washings with hot water and dilute acetic acid. The acetoxymercurial group enters the *p*-position of aryl nucleus at 2-position of thiazole nucleus¹⁰. The yields and analytical data of mercurials thus prepared are recorded in Table II.

TABLE I

No.	Ar ₂ .	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%S u l p h u r.	
					Found.	Reqd.
Ar ₁ = 2-fluoro-5-methylphenyl.						
1.	Phenyl	130-40°	71%	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ FS	10.88	11.27
2.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	103-104°	63	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ ClFS	10.12	10.04
3.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	150-52°	63	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ FS	10.51	10.74
4.	2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	87-88°	42	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ Br ₃ FS	5.00	6.14
Ar ₁ = 4-fluoro-2-methylphenyl.						
5.	Phenyl	138°	66	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ FB	11.01	11.27
6.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	115-17°	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ ClFS	9.42	10.04
7.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	120-21°	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ FS	10.02	10.74
Ar ₁ = 4-fluorophenyl.						
8.	Phenyl	106-10°	58	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ FS	11.02	11.86
9.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	114-15°	51	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ FS	10.42	11.27

9. *Chem. Abs.*, 1950, 48, 2509.

10. Pujari and Rout, *this Journal*, 1954, 31, 257.

TABLE II

2-(p-Acetoxymercuri)-arylamino-4-substituted phenylthiazoles.

No.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Mercury.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1.	178-86°	72%	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ SHg	36.71	36.98
2.	*240°	71	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ ClF ₂ SHg	34.12	34.76
3.	150-51°	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ SHg	36.72	36.04
4.	168-67°	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ SHg	36.00	36.98
5.	153-54°	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ ClF ₂ SHg	34.51	34.76
6.	158°	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ SHg	36.11	36.04
7.	*142-43°	74	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ SHg	37.01	37.04
8.	139-41°	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ F ₂ SHg	36.12	36.98

N. B. The numbers correspond to the number of thiazole compound in Table I.

*The compounds partly melt and then decompose.

The pesticidal activity of the above compounds will be communicated in due course.

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